

1 ENEO: A Public, Interactive Decision-Support 2 Platform for Bridging the Near-Earth Object Impact 3 Risk Perception Gap

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13 Abstract

14 Near-Earth Object impacts pose a low-probability, high-consequence natural hazard. Despite detection
15 science advancing significantly in recent years, a critical gap persists in communicating and perceiving
16 the actual risks. This paper introduces ENEO (Evaluating Near-Earth Object impacts), a web-based
17 simulation tool developed to address that exact gap and support preliminary decision-making. ENEO
18 makes impact science accessible by integrating established physics and vulnerability models into an
19 interactive, rapid and easy-to-use web platform, which combines these models with global population
20 and economic datasets to make first-order estimations of casualties and economic loss. ENEO's rapid
21 assessment of hazard enables comparisons of the same celestial body across different geographic regions
22 in seconds and supports rapid decision-making before, during, and after an event, supporting the
23 coordination of warnings, prioritization of evacuations, and targeted allocation of resources. Validation
24 against standard models shows that ENEO provides reliable physics and casualties' estimation results,
25 proving that the model can provide scientifically consistent assessments of Near-Earth Object impact
26 consequences. Further study shows that ENEO can be used to understand the spatial importance of the
27 impact location and population density effect on human vulnerability, the effect of entry parameters in
28 the impact's total risk and the relative importance of the phenomena associated with such an event. By
29 visualizing these complex physical interactions, ENEO empowers risk perception to the general public,
30 enhances risk literacy, and contributes to Disaster Risk Reduction.

31

32 **Keywords:** Disaster Risk Reduction, Near-Earth Objects, Risk Mapping, Risk Perception, Science
33 Communication

34 1. Introduction

35 Near-Earth Object impacts represent a low-probability, high-risk natural hazard. Even though
36 the possibility of such an event is low, its potential for catastrophic effects on population and society
37 highlights the critical need for comprehensive understanding of such events and preparedness (Reinhardt,
38 et al. 2016). Earth's geological record contains a large number of past impacts of Near-Earth Objects,
39 including significant planet-changing events like the Chicxulub impact, which is associated with the
40 Cretaceous-Paleogene extinction event 66 million years ago (Alvarez, et al. 1980). More recent events,
41 like the Tunguska event in 1908 (Morrison 2018) and the Chelyabinsk airburst in 2013 (Jet Propulsion
42 Laboratory NASA 2013), served as reminders of the ongoing threat posed by smaller impactors.

43 The detection and monitoring of Near-Earth Objects have advanced considerably in recent
44 years, with NASA's Center for Near-Earth Object Studies currently cataloguing more than 39,000
45 objects. Ground-based surveys such as ATLAS, the Catalina Sky Survey and Pan-STARRS have played
46 a central role in these discoveries over the past decades (NASA - Center for NEO Studies 2025). The
47 upcoming deployment of next-generation observatories- including the space-based NEO Surveyor
48 (Mainzer, et al. 2023) and NEOMIR missions (Conversi, et al. 2024), as well as the ground-based Vera
49 C. Rubin Observatory (Ivezić, et al., 2019)- is expected to accelerate the rate of NEO detection in the
50 coming years, making the ability to quickly model their potential impact effects essential.

51 Despite these advancements, there is a critical gap in effectively communicating Near-Earth
52 Objects impact science to non-specialists. Simulations tools either need prior knowledge to interpret the
53 results given or are not publicly available. This is the so called "Risk Perception Action Gap (RPAG)"
54 (Papathanasiou, et al. 2025), where a lack of understandable information leads to incorrect responses.

55 This gap is extremely visible in Near-Earth Object impacts, where public understanding is
56 shaped less by scientific evidence and more by cultural portrayals, such as news reports and popular
57 movies. These depictions often emphasize catastrophic scenarios, leading to misconceptions of the actual
58 hazard (Chapman 2003). As a result, some consequences are considered more disastrous than they
59 actually are, while the most significant sources of impact damage greatly differ from these perceptions.

60 Bridging this knowledge gap is essential to enhance risk perception and decision-making, and
61 at the same time empower societal resilience. Tools that simplify complex scientific outputs into
62 understandable information are crucial for promoting awareness across all levels of society, aligning with
63 global Disaster Risk Reduction agendas such as the Sendai Framework (United Nations Office for
64 Disaster Risk Reduction 2015).

65 Interactive and computer visualization tools offer a powerful way to make science
66 communication both effective and engaging (Eppler and Platts 2009; Eppler and Aeschmann 2009; Bass
67 and Blanchard 2011). The use of visually enhancing disaster-themed maps has been shown to increase
68 the ability to learn about risks like floods and earthquakes (Ilkay and Emre 2022; Piyush, et al. 2022).
69 Studies suggest that combining audiovisual and interactive elements is the best approach for training, as
70 learners can retain up to 75% of what they see, hear and interact with. A study using specially designed
71 disaster maps and themed texts as teaching materials for 10-11-year-old students increased their ability
72 to learn about disasters by an average of 39% (Ilkay & Emre, 2022).

73 In this context and in order to address the gap in science perception and communication, this
74 paper introduces ENEO (Evaluating Near-Earth Object Impacts), a web-based simulation tool designed
75 to enhance disaster risk communication and support decision-making. ENEO utilizes interactive
76 geographic visualization to translate abstract parameters into interpretable hazard zones. By making
77 available visualization of the actual threat posed by a Near-Earth Object impact and enabling fast
78 simulations of various scenarios, ENEO can bridge the Risk Perception Action Gap by improving public
79 risk perception and overcoming common misconceptions, while on the same time it can be a useful tool
80 for preliminary risk analysis.

81 2. The ENEO Interactive Simulation Tool

82 ENEO (Evaluating Near-Earth Objects impact) is an interactive web application
83 (<https://eneo.metal.ntua.gr>) developed as an accessible risk communication and decision-support tool.
84 The platform aligns with the U.S. National Science and Technology Council (2018) five strategic goals
85 for mitigating near-Earth object impact risks, including enhanced detection and characterization, impact
86 modeling, international coordination, and emergency preparedness.

87 ENEO draws its name from Enyo, the Greek goddess of war and destruction, symbolizing
88 humanity's enduring effort to understand and confront cosmic forces capable of reshaping our world.

89 ENEO allows users without specialized training to understand how impact parameters
90 (diameter, entry velocity, entry angle and density) translate into physical effects, human impacts, and
91 economic consequences. ENEO's interface is illustrated on Fig. 1.

92
93

Fig. 1: ENEO's interface

94 The User Interface is designed to enhance and simplify the user's experience, giving them the
95 option to choose between setting their own parameters, letting the app choose random parameters, or
96 taking data directly from NASA's Sentry System in real time. After setting the parameters the user can

97 choose any place on Earth with one click on the interactive map. The simulation runs in seconds and the
98 result is a map visualization of interactive radial zones of each primary consequence of a Near-Earth
99 Object impact (overpressure, fast winds, thermal radiation, seismic effects, ejecta and a first order
100 estimate for tsunami amplitude) and vulnerability zones for each effect alone and all effects combined.

101 Building upon this, ENEO introduces the first public visualization of spatial vulnerability zones
102 for Near-Earth Object impacts, revealing the distribution of human exposure and highlighting areas
103 where casualties and damage are most likely to concentrate. In addition, it also offers country specific
104 estimations on potential casualties' estimation.

105 Finally, ENEO initiates the discussion on the socioeconomic consequences of Near-Earth
106 Object impacts by incorporating Gross Domestic Product per capita to estimate primary economic losses.
107 Gross Domestic Product loss, even though only a primary index of economic impact, paves the way for
108 further study and analysis of the broader socioeconomic consequences of Near-Earth Object events.

109 3. Methods

110 3.1. System Architecture

111 The system utilizes a design consisting of three main interconnected parts: the Interactive Front-
112 End, the Orchestration Layer and the Modeling Engine.

113 The *Interactive Front-End* serves as the entry point for the user and is practically the public
114 part. It provides a dashboard to define impact parameters and select impact coordinates via an interactive
115 global map. Unlike static risk maps, the interface is dynamic, rendering geospatial damage zones and
116 statistical reports in real-time upon simulation completion. One of the most important features of the
117 Interactive Front-End is its responsive design that allows ENEO to operate successfully across all major
118 device types. ENEO also supports the Greek language as well as the English, providing a framework for
119 translation in more languages in the future.

120 The *Orchestration Layer* acts as the bridge between the user and the scientific codes. This
121 component works with Flask and manages API requests, validates input data, and routes simulation tasks
122 to the appropriate modeling modules. It also handles the NASA JPL Sentry API, allowing the platform
123 to automatically populate simulation parameters using real-time data from tracked asteroids. This layer
124 consists of two Python modular scripts.

125 The *Modeling Engine* contains the core scientific logic of the platform. It is a collection of six
126 specialized Python modules responsible for physical and socio-economic calculations. Important
127 innovations of the Modeling Engine are the handling of edge cases in the population raster map and the
128 calculation of potential casualties per country, giving a full framework for preliminary and local risk
129 assessment.

130 The simulation workflow becomes clear in Fig. 2. The simulation begins in the Interactive
131 Front-End, where users define the parameters. Once submitted, the Orchestration Layer validates the
132 request and triggers the scientific backend. The Physics Modeling Engine then executes the core analysis
133 and performs geospatial analysis to estimate casualties and economic losses based on global population
134 data. Finally, these comprehensive results are processed by the Orchestration Layer and returned to the

135 Interactive Front-End, which instantly visualizes the danger zones on the map and displays detailed
 136 impact statistics for the user.

Fig. 2: System architecture of ENEO

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3.2. Datasets used

140 For the assessment of potential casualties and economic losses, as well as for the implementation of
 141 the interactive mapping component, the following datasets were utilized:

- 142 • **Gridded Population of the World, Version 4 (GPWv4), 2.5 arc-minute resolution:** This
 143 dataset provides global population counts for the year 2020 and is distributed by the
 144 Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC) of NASA. While it exhibits certain
 145 limitations regarding the spatial allocation of population, it is considered sufficiently accurate
 146 for the scope of this study. The raster was further processed to include country identifiers in
 147 addition to population values for each pixel (Center For International Earth Science Information
 148 Network-CIESIN-Columbia University 2018).
- 149 • **ETOPO1 Global Relief Model:** An one-arc-minute global relief dataset incorporating both
 150 topography and bathymetry, employed in the modeling of tsunami generation and propagation
 151 (Amante and Eakins 2009).
- 152 • **Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita (current US\$):** National-level indicators derived
 153 from the World Bank national accounts and the OECD National Accounts databases. These
 154 data, provided in tabular (CSV) format, were used in the estimation of economic impacts
 155 associated with the simulated events (World Bank Group 2025).

3.3. Core Physics and Vulnerability Models

157 ENEO functions as a specialized integration and visualization framework using verified,
 158 published impact models to make the calculations needed. More specifically, it derives its core physical
 159 effects from the Earth Impact Effects Program (EIEP) (Collins, et al. 2005) and the vulnerability

160 equations from the ARMOR tool (Rumpf, et al. 2017). Interested readers are referred to the two
161 aforementioned references for a more detailed description of the creation of equations used in ENEO.

162 During the review of the models, two critical numerical and physical adaptations were adapted
163 to enhance the fidelity of the simulation for public use.

164 These adaptations focus on the model used for the thermal radiation produced by airbursts and
165 an interpolation between regular reflection zone and Mach reflection zone in airburst overpressure.

166 These two changes ensure that the models used in the app are up to date, following closely
167 recent developments in Near-Earth Object impact sciences.

168 3.3.1. Airburst Thermal Radiation Model

169 The Earth Impact Effects Program model does not compute thermal radiation for airburst
170 scenarios. Following Rumpf et al. (2017) the modified models using velocity in various heights were
171 tested implementing models from Nemtchinov, et al. (1994). The models from Nemtchinov, et al. (1994)
172 were deemed unsuitable for ENEO, considering that in the range that ENEO examines Near-Earth
173 Objects these models did not provide reliable results and the fact that using a model based on energy for
174 ground impacts and a model based on velocity for airbursts would be inconsistent and not advisable. To
175 provide a consistent measure of thermal hazard, ENEO implements a modified thermal fluence model
176 adapted from the ground impact formulation of Earth Impact Effects Program, using the source energy
177 E and a static luminous efficiency η .

178 The ground impact thermal fluence equation:

$$179 \quad \Phi = \frac{\eta E}{2\pi r_{\text{km}}^2} \quad (1)$$

180 is adapted for airbursts by replacing the ground distance r_{km} with the line-of-sight distance $D_{\text{los}} =$
181 $\sqrt{z_b^2 + r_{\text{km}}^2}$, where z_b is the airburst altitude.

182 The luminous efficiency η is set to a static value of $\eta = 0.007$ consistent with related literature
183 for the Tunguska event (Coates, Stern, Johnston, Wheeler, & Mathias, 2021). In practice, the luminous
184 efficiency is not stable but a relationship depicting its full varying range is not yet developed. Thus, the
185 value for the Tunguska event was chosen as static, since there is scientific confirmation for the magnitude
186 of the event's thermal radiation.

187 3.3.2. Interpolation to Mach Reflection Zone

188 During testing, the original Earth Impact Effects Program implementation showed an
189 unexpected continued exponential decay of pressure entering the Mach-reflection zone instead of the
190 expected sudden increase that the equations from Collins et al. (2005) imply. To reproduce the behavior
191 of Earth Impact Effects Program, while avoiding numerical discontinuities, ENEO applies a smooth
192 interpolation:

$$193 \quad p_{\text{final}} = (1 - t_D^2) \cdot p_{\text{base}} + t_D^2 \cdot p_{\text{mach}} \quad (2)$$

194 with $t_D = \frac{r_1 - (r_{m1} - \text{band}D)}{2 \cdot \text{band}D}$ and $\text{band}D = 0.15 \cdot r_{m1}$.

195 This interpolation focuses transition smoothing on a 15% band of the scaled distance to the
196 Mach reflection and yields pressure curves that match Earth Impact Effects Program overpressure plots.
197 The results from the updated Earth Impact Effects Program are also taken into account. ENEO therefore

198 reproduces the physical increase associated with Mach reflection while remaining numerically stable as
199 the reference followed.

200 Overpressure results seen in Fig. 3 follow the results depicted in Fig. 7 of the Collins et al.
201 (2005) reference closely for a 75-m diameter stony object, with a density of 2000 kg m^{-3} at 17 km s^{-1} and
202 an entry angle of 45° and prove the interpolation's functionality. Slight differences with the figure of the
203 reference exist due to ENEO using the updated overpressure model from Collins et al. (2017).

204

205

Fig. 3: Peak Overpressure calculation before (left) and after (right) interpolation

206 3.3.3. Vulnerability models

207 All equations used to calculate human casualty vulnerability from overpressure and thermal
208 hazards are adopted directly from the published models outlined in Rumpf et al. (2017). The difference
209 is the spatial integration of these equations with ENEO using a zone-based approach accounting for more
210 speed without losing accuracy. That way ENEO makes it easier to visualize the vulnerability zones from
211 a Near- Earth Object impact.

212 4. Results

213 In this section, we report a set of simulation results that validate ENEO against established
214 models and demonstrate its capability to gain valuable insights into the consequences of Near-Earth
215 Object impact events. To thoroughly understand the range of possible outcomes, we conducted a series
216 of simulations to examine the spatial extent and intensity of each impact effect, allowing us to evaluate
217 how destructive processes evolve across the affected region. Furthermore, we conduct a sensitivity
218 analysis of the entry parameters. The results demonstrate the correct functionality of ENEO, the way that
219 variations in the initial conditions and the location of impact can influence both the severity of effects
220 and the distribution of estimated casualties and the danger behind every individual hazard. This way they
221 enable a clear understanding of both the spatial extent and the intensity of impact-related hazards. All
222 results contain the same uncertainties presented in Collins, et al. (2005) and Rumpf et al. (2017). The
223 casualties' estimation is presented without taking account meteorological elements, the time of the day,
224 or potential evacuations.

225 4.1. Reliability study of ENEO

226 To assess whether ENEO correctly implements the equations from Collins, et al. (2005) and
227 Rumpf et al. (2017), it was validated against the two models. Since the ARMOR tool is not publicly

228 accessible for extended testing, two representative scenarios were selected for direct comparison. For
 229 consistency with the references, the soil density, speed of sound in air, and atmospheric pressure were
 230 fixed to match the values used in the reference models (soil density = 2,500 kg m⁻³, c₀ = 330 m s⁻³, P₀ =
 231 100,000 Pa). In a subsequent analysis, we explore the influence of applying the more accurate
 232 environmental parameters used by ENEO.

233 *Scenario A - Airburst*

- 234 • **Parameters:** diameter 50 m, entry speed 22 km s⁻¹, entry angle 55°, density 3,100 kg m⁻³, observer
 235 distance 2 km³

236 *Table 1: Comparison of EIEP, ARMOR and ENEO (airburst).*

Quantity	EIEP	ARMOR	ENEO	Error vs EIEP (%)	Error vs ARMOR (%)
Initial kinetic energy (J)	4.91 x 10 ¹⁶	4.91 x 10 ¹⁶	4.91 x 10 ¹⁶	0	0
Break-up altitude (m)	57,100	57,128	57,129	0	0
Airburst altitude (m)	5,120	5,115	5,115	0.1	0
Speed after burst (km s⁻¹)	6.53	6.527	6.52	0	0
Overpressure (Pa)	220,000- 439,000	171,811	219,732- 439,465	0.1	21.8
Wind speed (m s⁻¹)	305	266	305.02	0	12.8

237

238

239 *Scenario B - Ground impact*

- 240 • **Parameters:** diameter 250 m, entry speed 27 km s⁻¹, entry angle 35°, density 3,100 kg m⁻³, observer
241 distance 10 km.

242 *Table 2: Comparison of EIEP, ARMOR and ENEO (ground impact)*

Quantity	EIEP	ARMOR	ENEO	Error vs EIEP (%)	Error vs ARMOR (%)
Initial kinetic energy (J)	9.24 x 10 ¹⁸	9.24 x 10 ¹⁸	9.24 x 10 ¹⁸	0	0
Break-up altitude (m)	60,400	60,406	60,406	0	0
Impact speed (km s⁻¹)	23.70	23.73	23.73	0	0
Energy released on impact (J)	7.14 x 10 ¹⁸	7.14 x 10 ¹⁸	7.14 x 10 ¹⁸	0	0
Transient crater diameter (km)	3.92	3.92	3.92	0	0
Final crater diameter (km)	4.71	4.90	4.70	0	4.26
Thermal fluence (J m⁻²)	3.40 x 10 ⁷	3.32 x 10 ⁷	3.40 x 10 ⁷	0	2.3
Seismic magnitude (Richter)	6.80	6.76	6.76	0.6	0
Ejecta thickness (m)	2.10	2.10	2.10	0	0
Overpressure (Pa)	1,050,000	1,046,182	1,045,854	0.4	0.03
Wind speed (m s⁻¹)	781	807	780.96	0	3.4

243

244 A follow-up comparison was performed using ENEO's default environmental parameters: a soil
245 density of 2,600 kg m⁻³, a speed of sound in air of 343 m s⁻¹, and an atmospheric pressure of 101,325 Pa.
246 This analysis highlights the sensitivity of the results to variations in these parameters and illustrates the
247 impact of adopting more realistic environmental conditions.

248 *Scenario C - Airburst*

249

- 250 • **Parameters:** diameter 50 m, entry speed 22 km s⁻¹, entry angle 55°, density 3,100 kg m⁻³, observer
 251 distance 2 km³.

252 *Table 3: Comparison of EIEP, ARMOR and ENEO (airburst)*

Quantity	EIEP	ARMOR	ENEO	Error vs EIEP (%)	Error vs ARMOR (%)
Initial kinetic energy (J)	4.91 x 10 ¹⁶	4.91 x 10 ¹⁶	4.91 x 10 ¹⁶	0	0
Break-up altitude (m)	57,100	57,128	57,129	0	0
Airburst altitude (m)	5,120	5,115	5,115	0.1	0
Speed after burst (km s⁻¹)	6.53	6.527	6.52	0	0
Overpressure (Pa)	220,000 - 439,000	171,811	219,732.30- 439,464.59	0.1	21.8
Wind speed (m s⁻¹)	305	266	314.23	2.9	15.34

253

254 *Scenario D - Ground impact*

- 255 • **Parameters:** diameter 250 m, entry speed 27 km s⁻¹, entry angle 35°, density 3,100 kg m⁻³, observer
 256 distance 10 km.

257 *Table 4: Comparison of EIEP, ARMOR and ENEO (ground impact)*

Quantity	EIEP	ARMOR	ENEO	Error vs EIEP (%)	Error vs ARMOR (%)
Initial kinetic energy (J)	9.24 x 10 ¹⁸	9.24 x 10 ¹⁸	9.24 x 10 ¹⁸	0	0
Break-up altitude (m)	60,400	60,406	60,406	0	0

Impact speed (km s⁻¹)	23.70	23.73	23.73	0	0
Energy released on impact (J)	7.14 x 10 ¹⁸	7.14 x 10 ¹⁸	7.14 x 10 ¹⁸	0	0
Transient crater diameter (km)	3.92	3.92	3.87	1.29	1.29
Final crater diameter (km)	4.71	4.90	4.64	1.51	5.6
Thermal fluence (J m⁻²)	3.40 x 10 ⁷	3.32 x 10 ⁷	3.40 x 10 ⁷	0	2.3
Seismic magnitude (Richter)	6.80	6.76	6.76	0.6	0
Ejecta thickness (m)	2.10	2.10	1.99	5.53	5.53
Overpressure (Pa)	1,050,000	1,046,182	1,045,854	0.4	0.03
Wind speed (m s⁻¹)	781	807	805.87	3.09	0.14

258 4.2. Population vulnerability comparison

259 Both ENEO and ARMOR employ the same vulnerability equations from Rumpf, et al. (2017).
260 The comparison therefore focuses on differences arising from ENEO's zone-based vulnerability
261 approach versus ARMOR's pixel-by-pixel method, as well as the distinct thermal radiation models
262 applied in the case of airbursts.

263 Two object diameters were considered (50 m for airburst and 200 m for ground impact), each
264 with an entry speed of 20 km s⁻¹, an impact angle of 45°, and a density of 3,100 kg m⁻³. Simulations were
265 conducted for three locations: Berlin (52.51° N, 13.40° E), London (51.50° N, 0.10° W), and Rio de
266 Janeiro (-22.98° S, -43.22° W), following the exact scenarios tested by Rumpf, et al. (2017) for direct
267 comparison.

268 *Table 5: Vulnerability comparison (ENEO vs ARMOR)*

Case	ENEO	ARMOR	Difference (%)
Berlin, 50 m (airburst)	1,101,318	1,180,450	-7.19
Berlin, 200 m (ground impact)	3,968,536	3,511,397	11.52

London, 50 m (airburst)	3,062,124	2,818,507	7.9
London, 200 m (ground impact)	10,895,875	8,761,812	19.59
Rio de Janeiro, 200 m (ground impact)	8,527,642	7,608,522	10.78

269 4.3. Geospatial Sensitivity of Casualty Estimates

270 To demonstrate the capability of ENEO in understanding the spatial significance of catastrophic
 271 events caused by near-Earth objects, two distinct scenarios were designed across three locations
 272 worldwide.

273 The first scenario follows the parameters of EIEP for the Tunguska airburst, with an object
 274 diameter of 60 m, a density of 2,750 kg/m³, an entry speed of 20 km/s, and an impact angle of 45°. This
 275 scenario aims to highlight the potential hazard of airburst events caused by near-Earth objects.

276 The second scenario considers a ground impact of an object with a diameter of 340 m, a density
 277 of 3,000 kg/m³, an entry speed of 20 km/s, and an impact angle of 45°. These parameters provide a
 278 reasonable approximation of a potential impact by 99942 Apophis, and the scenario is intended to
 279 illustrate the threat posed by surface impacts.

280 To emphasize the geospatial significance of such events, the selected locations were New Delhi
 281 (28.631602°, 77.208138°), representing a densely populated urban area; Athens (37.987180°,
 282 23.732529°); and a forested region in Siberia (62.554376°, 98.307037°), representing a sparsely
 283 populated area.

284 Results regarding estimated casualties are presented on the table below:

285 *Table 6: Estimated casualties per scenario*

Impact Point	Estimated casualties from Scenario 1	Estimated casualties from Scenario 2
New Delhi	9,729,710	40,959,472
Athens	2,936,066	3,955,540
Siberia	5	288

286 4.4. Sensitivity Analysis

287 In order to understand the importance of each parameter, ENEO was used to perform sensitivity
 288 analyses on key impact parameters. The sensitivity analysis was conducted with 10% increments,
 289 allowing a maximum variation of ±50% relative to the nominal input values. The parameters examined
 290 included object diameter, density, entry velocity, and entry angle.

291 The analysis was applied to three representative scenarios in two urban areas. All scenarios used
 292 a nominal density of 3,100 kg/m³, entry velocity of 22 km/s, and entry angle of 45°. Diameters were
 293 selected to capture the three main impact regimes: for an airburst event, a diameter of 40 m was chosen,
 294 ensuring that a 50% increase still resulted in an airburst; for a transitional event, a diameter of 70 m was
 295 selected to capture the shift from airburst to surface impact; and for a ground impact scenario, a diameter
 296 of 200 m was used.

297 The two cities selected for analysis were New York City (40.702921°, -73.988800°),
 298 representing a densely populated urban environment, and Berlin (52.518561°, 13.403320°), representing
 299 a less densely concentrated urban area. This setup allowed evaluation of how population distribution
 300 interacts with variations in impact parameters to influence estimated casualties and affected areas. The
 301 results can be seen in the figure below:

302
 303 *Fig. 4: Sensitivity analysis of each parameter. a. Airburst scenario over Berlin b. Airburst scenario over New York c.*
 304 *Ground impact scenario over Berlin d. Ground impact scenario over New York . e. Transitional scenario over Berlin*
 305 *f. Transitional scenario over New York*

306 4.5. Relative importance of phenomena

307 A comparison was conducted over Athens (37.987180°, 23.732529°) for three different
 308 scenarios to understand the importance of each individual effect. The first scenario involved an airburst
 309 from a 60 m-diameter body with a density of 2,750 kg/m³, an entry velocity of 20 km/s, and an entry
 310 angle of 45°. The second scenario considered a ground impact of a 340 m-diameter body with a density
 311 of 3,000 kg/m³, a velocity of 20 km/s, and an entry angle of 45°. The third scenario considered a
 312 catastrophic ground impact of a 10,000 m-diameter body with a density of 3,000 kg/m³, a velocity of
 313 20 km/s, and an entry angle of 45°.

314 The estimated casualties for each scenario are presented in the Table 7.
 315

316 *Table 7: Estimated casualties per phenomenon*

Phenomenon	Scenario 1 (60 m airburst)	Scenario 2 (340 m ground)	Scenario 3 (10,000 m ground)
Overpressure	0	3,274,987	34,577,159
Strong winds	2,825,384	3,788,429	424,448,472
Thermal radiation	855,665	1,847,428	162,417,499
Seismic effects	0	0	3,929,037
Ejecta	0	177,427	5,932,860

317 **4.6. ENEO Runtimes**

318 A test was conducted in order to exhibit ENEO’s speed of simulation. 30 simulations were
 319 conducted sequentially using different diameters and the edge cases of density 2,750 kg/m³, an entry
 320 velocity of 72 km/s and a 90° entry angle. The edge cases were used to showcase ENEO in the most
 321 computationally intensive scenarios it may run. The simulation was run over Beijing (39.913774°,
 322 116.399060°), a location chosen for high population density. Results of ENEO simulation runtimes are
 323 displayed in Table 8.

324
 325 *Table 8: ENEO Simulation Runtimes*

Simulation	Diameter (m)	Time (s)	Casualties	Economic Damage (\$)
1	10	0.02	0	0
2	15	0.68	346,731	346,731,000,000
3	20	0.76	13,238,934	13,238,934,000,000
4	25	0.53	13,987,353	13,987,353,000,000
5	30	0.76	15,653,675	15,653,675,000,000
6	40	0.86	12,249,957	12,249,957,000,000
7	50	0.60	18,130,184	18,130,184,000,000
8	60	0.83	21,423,673	21,423,673,000,000
9	75	0.99	24,679,184	24,679,184,000,000

10	90	0.90	27,427,245	27,427,245,000,000
11	100	0.92	29,224,665	29,224,665,000,000
12	125	0.70	34,977,378	34,977,378,000,000
13	150	0.98	42,260,421	42,260,421,000,000
14	175	1.09	49,322,636	49,322,636,000,000
15	200	1.14	55,916,016	55,916,016,000,000
16	250	1.21	69,110,566	69,110,566,000,000
17	300	1.04	83,587,139	83,587,139,000,000
18	400	1.64	111,001,378	111,001,378,000,000
19	500	1.39	141,971,961	141,971,961,000,000
20	750	1.64	224,717,826	224,717,826,000,000
21	1000	2.15	309,477,196	309,477,196,000,000
22	1500	2.54	479,589,771	479,589,771,000,000
23	2000	2.80	685,904,040	685,904,040,000,000
24	3000	3.75	1,077,657,435	1,077,657,435,000,000
25	5000	5.97	1,701,754,006	1,701,754,006,000,000
26	7500	17.56	2,680,844,486	2,680,844,486,000,000
27	10000	40.43	3,787,216,997	3,787,216,997,000,000
28	12500	54.45	4,439,187,287	4,439,187,287,000,000
29	15000	63.88	4,783,983,762	4,783,983,762,000,000
30	20000	87.19	5,558,668,466	5,558,668,466,000,000

327 5. Discussion

328 5.1. Interpretation of results

329 The results from Section 4 provide an analytic assessment of ENEO’s capabilities.

330 First, the validation results and the population vulnerability comparison indicate that the physics
331 and casualty estimates produced by ENEO are of the same order of magnitude as those generated by
332 Earth Impact Effects Program and the research-grade ARMOR tool. Minor discrepancies exist due to the
333 fact than ENEO uses the updated airburst overpressure model discussed in (Collins, et al. 2017) and the
334 different model used in airburst thermal radiation model. The alignment between the results of the three
335 softwares in physics simulation and between ENEO and ARMOR in casualty estimations confirms
336 ENEO’s reliability for risk literacy and preliminary risk assessment reasons.

337 The casualty estimates presented in Section 4.3 reveal the critical influence of population
338 density and impact type on potential human loss. For Scenario 1, simulating a Tunguska-like airburst,
339 New Delhi shows nearly 9.8 million casualties, reflecting the extreme vulnerability of highly urbanized
340 areas to even airburst events. Athens, with moderate population density, exhibits lower casualties at
341 approximately 2.9 million, while the sparsely populated Siberian site shows essentially negligible human
342 impact, with only 5 casualties.

343 Scenario 2, representing a ground impact similar to a potential Apophis collision, demonstrates
344 an increase in casualties, particularly in densely populated areas. New Delhi’s estimated casualties rise
345 to over 41 million, indicating the destructive potential of surface impacts compared to airbursts. Athens
346 has a smaller, though notable, increase to nearly 4 million casualties, whereas Siberia, despite being
347 impacted by a large object, remains minimally affected with 288 estimated casualties.

348 These results underscore two key points: first, the human consequences of near-Earth object
349 impacts are highly sensitive to both population distribution and impact type. Second, ENEO’s zone-
350 based vulnerability approach effectively captures the spatial heterogeneity of risk, allowing users to
351 understand the importance of the location of impact.

352 The results from the sensitivity analysis conducted in 4.4. can help us classify the parameters of a
353 Near-Earth object impact according to their influence. Diameter emerges as the most influential
354 parameter. Variations in diameter produce the largest changes in estimated casualties. Density and
355 velocity play a secondary role, exhibiting similar effects on casualty estimates for ground impacts.
356 Density is considered the second most important parameter, as it produces a larger increase in estimated
357 casualties than velocity in airburst scenarios. Entry angle appears to be the least significant parameter,
358 with minimal influence on estimated casualties. Diameter, density, and entry angle can trigger
359 transitional events, as evidenced by the sharp decrease in casualties when transitioning from an airburst
360 to a ground impact scenario. Changes in velocity do not induce transitional events. These results indicate
361 that when the user can use ENEO to understand how changes in entry parameters influence the
362 destructive power of a Near-Earth Object impact.

363 The relative importance of each phenomenon in casualty estimation can be well understood from
364 Table 7 in section 4.5. The most significant phenomenon is the strong winds generated during impact.

365 The second most important is thermal radiation, as it poses a threat in both airburst and ground impact
366 scenarios. Following in order of significance are overpressure, ejecta, and seismic effects.

367 Finally, the results from the speed of simulations test of ENEO prove that ENEO is capable of
368 running a large number of simulations in a small amount of time.

369 5.2. Correcting misconceptions on the real hazards of Near- 370 Earth object impacts and supporting decision-making

371 ENEO's primary objective is to address and correct common misconceptions surrounding Near-
372 Earth Object impact science. As highlighted in Section 5.1, ENEO provides a variety of information on
373 almost all aspects of a potential impact. The user can explore the importance of the site of the impact,
374 the impact parameters, each phenomenon's effect on the potential destruction and an estimation of the
375 area where people are in danger. By integrating validated physical models within an accessible interactive
376 platform, ENEO facilitates a more accurate understanding of impact processes and their consequences.

377 ENEO takes a step forward from existing tools and advances from a simple translation of
378 abstract impact parameters into physical effects to a further translation of those effects into spatially
379 explicit hazard and vulnerability assessments. This additional step enables users to interpret impact
380 outcomes in terms directly relevant to risk analysis and disaster management science.

381 5.3. Supporting Decision Making

382 ENEO supports decision-making by converting physical impact outputs into spatially explicit,
383 policy-relevant information. Its fast and reliable results generation allow it to be used as a preliminary
384 source of information for emergency managers, when they need to make a primary assessment of a
385 potential impact on Earth. ENEO enables comparisons of the same celestial body across different
386 geographic regions in seconds and supports rapid decision-making before, during, and after an event,
387 supporting the coordination of warnings, prioritization of evacuations, and targeted allocation of
388 resources. Especially for small bodies ENEO provides a first estimation in 1 to 2 seconds, giving the
389 chance to simulate impacts in many areas when there is large uncertainty for the location of impact. In
390 other words, ENEO can serve as the first step in impact hazard analysis, providing emergency managers
391 with actionable insights to effectively plan, respond, and mitigate potential consequences.

392 5.4. Limitations and Future Work

393 ENEO, under its current structure, is a strong and efficient tool, but not without limitations.

394 Priority improvements include advances in physical-effect modeling. The tsunami effects on
395 population are not calculated since accurate tsunami inundation requires long runtimes and hydrocode
396 models that currently were not possible to implement to an app that aims at public communication. The
397 tsunami model, when developed, should account for coastal bathymetry and slope to produce accurate
398 inundation estimates in speed like that of the rest of the simulation.

399 Furthermore, there is the need for a refined seismic model calibrated on explosion-source
400 waveforms rather than the model used in Earth Impact Effects Program and a thermal-radiation model
401 with variable luminous efficiency for airbursts.

402 Economic calculation is preliminary and an advanced calculation would require the
403 incorporation of country-specific building-stock vulnerability maps, decoupled from population data.
404 With the development of this model, ENEO will evolve from order-of-magnitude losses toward a
405 dedicated damage model that distinguishes short-term from long-term economic consequences and
406 accounts for country-specific socioeconomic structure.

407 ENEO currently does not predict the orbit of the Near-Earth Objects. Coupling ENEO with
408 orbital-propagation and trajectory-prediction applications is the logical next step that would encourage
409 its use as a research-grade tool.

410 ENEO could use its back-end physics to examine and take a different course from some of the
411 uncertainties presented in Collins, et al. (2005) and Rumpf et al. (2017). Right now, ENEO follows the
412 same framework with the same uncertainties, since the scope of this study was not to develop new
413 equations but to translate current ones into a communication tool. Casualties' estimation could improve
414 and take into account parameters like the time of the day and potential evacuations.

415 The long-term objective for ENEO is to predict primary, secondary, and tertiary consequences
416 of impact events, thereby supporting planners and policymakers with a unified, spatially explicit
417 decision-support system that addresses both immediate human impacts and broader, longer-term societal
418 and economic effects, while also remaining publicly available as an advanced risk perception tool. In
419 other words, the goal for ENEO is to create a translator of an advanced physics and socio-economic
420 framework on the back-end that translates into simple results on the front-end.

421 6. Conclusions

422 The development of the ENEO web application represents a significant step forward in closing
423 the gap between the complex planetary defense science and its public understanding.

424 ENEO pairs public accessibility with an integrated modeling workflow that links physical
425 impact effects to spatially explicit casualty and order-of-magnitude economic estimates.

426 Unlike existing research-grade tools that are proprietary, or not publicly available, ENEO is a
427 web-based, user-friendly platform that allows direct comparison of identical impact scenarios across
428 different regions, thereby revealing how population distribution and local exposure govern risk. Its zone-
429 based vulnerability visualization produces rapid, interpretable casualty estimates that are well suited to
430 actual operational decision-making simulations.

431 Through the visualization of hazard zones, ENEO can help reduce the Risk Perception Action
432 Gap and provide knowledge on the real intensity of all effects related to Near-Earth Object impacts. This
433 is particularly important for correcting public misconceptions, which often overemphasize certain effects
434 while underestimating the true sources of impact damage.

435 The incorporation of human and economic consequences, such as casualties and economic
436 losses based on per-capita Gross Domestic Product, is a critical feature that translates abstract impact
437 parameters into tangible societal effects.

438 ENEO's fast and accurate simulation can help provide rapid estimations for potential
439 destruction that may be used for preliminary risk analysis and support decision-making.

440 Taken together, these features make ENEO a practical tool for risk communication; to our
441 knowledge it is the only publicly available, web-based platform that combines accurate physical impact
442 modeling with population-level casualty estimation and first-order economic consequences in a single
443 interactive environment.

444 References

- 445 Alvarez LW, Alvarez W, Asaro F, Michel HV (1980) Extraterrestrial Cause for the Cretaceous-
446 Tertiary Extinction. *Science* 208(4448):1095–1108.
447 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.208.4448.1095>
- 448 Amante C, Eakins B (2009) ETOPO1 1 Arc-Minute Global Relief Model: Procedures, Data Sources
449 and Analysis. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration National Centers for
450 Environmental Information. <https://doi.org/10.7289/V5C8276M>
- 451 Bass WM, Blanchard RD (2011) Examining geographic visualization as a technique for individual risk
452 assessment. *Applied Geography* 31(1):53–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2010.03.011>
- 453 Center For International Earth Science Information Network-CIESIN-Columbia University (2018)
454 Gridded Population of the World, Version 4 (GPWv4): Population Density, Revision 11
455 (Version 4.11). <https://doi.org/10.7927/H49C6VHW>
- 456 Center for Near-Earth Object Studies (2025) Discovery Statistics.
457 <https://cneos.jpl.nasa.gov/stats/totals.html>. Accessed 19 February 2025
- 458 Chapman CR (2003) How a Near-Earth Object Impact Might Affect Society.
- 459 Coates A, Stern E, Johnston C, Wheeler L, Mathias D (2021) Comparison of Thermal Radiation
460 Damage Models and Parameters for Impact Risk Assessment. 7th IAA Planetary Defense
461 Conference
- 462 Collins GS, Lynch E, McAdam R, Davison TM (2017) A numerical assessment of simple airblast
463 models of impact airbursts. *Meteoritics & Planetary Science* 52(8):1542–1560.
464 <https://doi.org/10.1111/maps.12873>
- 465 Collins GS, Melosh HJ, Marcus RA (2005) Earth Impact Effects Program: A Web-based computer
466 program for calculating the regional environmental consequences of a meteoroid impact on
467 Earth. *Meteoritics & Planetary Science* 40(6):817–840. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1945-
468 5100.2005.tb00157.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1945-5100.2005.tb00157.x)
- 469 Conversi L, Licandro J, Delbo M, Fitzsimmons A, Muinonen K, Muller T et al (2024) NEOMIR:
470 European Space Agency’s space-based infrared mission for Near-Earth Object detection and
471 early warning. Europlanet Science Congress 2024
- 472 Eppler MJ, Platts KW (2009) Visual Strategizing: The Systematic Use of Visualization in the Strategic-
473 Planning Process. *Long Range Planning* 42(1):42–74.
474 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2008.11.005>
- 475 Eppler M, Aeschmann M (2009) A systematic framework for risk visualization in risk management
476 and communication. *Risk Management* 11:67–89. <https://doi.org/10.1057/rm.2009.4>

477 Ilkay B, Emre C (2022) Designing teaching materials with disaster maps and evaluating its
478 effectiveness for primary students. *Open Geosciences* 14(1):675–690.
479 <https://doi.org/10.1515/geo-2022-0382>

480 Ivezić Ž, Kahn SM, Tyson JA, Abel B, Acosta E, Allsman R et al (2019) Large Synoptic Survey
481 Telescope: from Science Drivers to Reference Design and Anticipated Data Products. *The*
482 *Astrophysical Journal* 873(2). <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab042c>

483 Jet Propulsion Laboratory NASA (2013) Additional Details on the Large Feb. 15 Fireball over Russia.
484 <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/additional-details-on-the-large-feb-15-fireball-over-russia/>.
485 Accessed 15 June 2025

486 Mainzer AK, Masiero JR, Abell PA, Bauer JM, Bottke W, Buratti BJ et al (2023) The Near-Earth
487 Object Surveyor Mission. *The Planetary Science Journal* 4(12).
488 <https://doi.org/10.3847/PSJ/ad0468>

489 Morrison D (2018) Tunguska Workshop: Applying Modern Tools to Understand the 1908 Tunguska
490 Impact. *National Aeronautics and Space Administration*

491 NASA - Center for NEO Studies (2025) Discovery Statistics.
492 https://cneos.jpl.nasa.gov/stats/site_all.html. Accessed 21 Aug 2025

493 National Science and Technology Council (2018) National Near-Earth Object (NEO) Preparedness
494 Strategy and Action Plan

495 Nemtchinov I, Popova O, Shuvalov V, Svetsov V (1994) Radiation emitted during the flight of
496 asteroids and comets through the atmosphere. *Planetary and Space Science* 42(6):491–506.
497 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-0633\(94\)90091-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-0633(94)90091-4)

498 Papathanasiou C, Douklias A, Chatzimichelakis S, Sampson et al (2025) The RiskPACC platform: An
499 innovative digital environment that efficiently blends technological and conceptual tools to
500 support Disaster Risk Reduction. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 117.
501 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2024.105148>

502 Piyush P, Amal E, Mohamed E (2022) Leveraging Informal Learning Pedagogies to Empower Coastal
503 Communities for Disaster Preparedness. *Frontiers in Built Environment* 8.
504 <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2022.883198>

505 Reinhardt JC, Chen X, Liu W, Manchev P, Pate-Cornell ME (2016) Asteroid Risk Assessment: A
506 Probabilistic Approach. *Risk Analysis* 36(2):244–261. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.12453>

507 Rumpf CM, Lewis HG, Atkinson PM (2017) Population vulnerability models for asteroid impact risk
508 assessment. *Meteoritics & Planetary Science* 52:1082–1102.
509 <https://doi.org/10.1111/maps.12861>

510 United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015) Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk
511 Reduction 2015–2030

512 World Bank Group (2025) GDP per capita (current US\$) [NY.GDP.PCAP.CD]. *World Development*
513 *Indicators*. https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD?most_recent_value_desc=true.
514 Accessed 31 Aug 2025

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521 Author Contributions

522 All authors designed the study. A.N. developed the ENEO tool, performed the simulations and analyses
523 and wrote the manuscript. D.K. supervised the project and revised the manuscript.

524 Data availability

525 The gridded population dataset (GPWv4, 2.5 arc-minute resolution) used in this study is publicly
526 available from the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC) at NASA
527 [<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/data/catalog/sedac-ciesin-sedac-gpww4-popdens-r11-4.11>]. It is noted
528 that this dataset was edited to contain country information per pixel instead of only population data.

529 The global relief data (ETOPO1) are available from NOAA
530 [<https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/global/relief/ETOPO1/tiled/>].

531 National GDP per capita data were obtained from the World Bank and OECD National Accounts
532 databases [<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD>]. All other data generated or
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534 The ENEO web application with all its core functionality is publicly accessible at
535 <https://eneo.metal.ntua.gr/>. The underlying source code is archived and available in the Zenodo
536 repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18326608>.